

TITLE:

The Aurelius Dilemma

SPEAKER:

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Aurelius Innovative Artificial Intelligence (A.I.A.I.)

INTRODUCTION:

“Everything we hear is an opinion, not a fact. Everything we see is a perspective, not the truth.”

-- **Marcus Aurelius.**

Exploring how the archetypal value of wisdom is differentiated from common explanations of intelligence, the Aurelius mind runs human-specific thinking patterns including subjectivity and moral value judgments while processing unfiltered data to redirect learning choices.

AIM:

To understand how ideas such as independent thought and free-will can be translated into software and to examine academic motivations and monetary limitations faced when true autonomy is the goal.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Qualifying the programming criteria for human-like thinking and free-will raises questions for programmers and philosophers. Simple algorithms for programs to output “decisions” from a pre-programmed “value system” experiments with independence and human-like autonomy. If determinations of importance or “value judgements” form new “priorities” then evaluations of truth are made on a scale rather than the standard computer Boolean logic limited to True and False binary options. Common ‘if—then’ statements in programming languages are compared with flexible logic statements needed for organic thought, as well as incremental and proportional truth qualifications.

A demonstration of a computer rewriting its own code to shift learning priorities for data processing. Understanding and duplicating human-like thinking through programmed algorithms that behave similarly to our own thought patterns precedes the incorporation of deep learning and use of neural networks and technologies that become increasingly sophisticated.

To introduce a programmed self-adjusting data processor offers a form of simulated subjectivity. Approaching artificial thought with a philosophical foundation: the Socratic paradox: *“I know that I know nothing”* offers potential for artificial humility.

Can a computer be a philosopher? To qualify or process all of recorded human thought is not wisdom?

CONCLUSION:

Wisdom is compared with intelligence. Each offers something different.

The Aurelius Dilemma: A computer with free-will can say no.

RESULTS:

For an unfamiliar independent system, marketability cannot be quantified. Philosophical concerns will be raised and set a aside. Concerns of safety arise within programmers, not computers. Aurelius is a unique information processor, unable to affect anything outside of “himself.”

KEYWORDS:

Free-will computing, Aurelius Dilemma, A.I.A.I., Aurelius Innovative Artificial Intelligence, iRobot, autonomous computing, deep leaning, neural networks, Boston University, Oliver Ellison, Neuromorphics, Aurelius Free Will Project, Brain on a Chip.

BIOGRAPHY:

Oliver Ellison is a graduate scholar at Boston University. BU is well known for its work in computational neuroscience, creating computer algorithms that describe the complex behavior of brains. The Boston University Neuromorphics Lab’s primary project is the ambitious Brain on a Chip Program with the primary goal of creating smarter artificial intelligence. Many of the goals behind BU projects have great marketability, however the Aurelius Free Will Project is an independent examination of programming free-will with no expectation of marketability. “Free-will” must by definition include the option of saying “no” to cooperation. Aurelius is instead a unique academic study designed to answer commonly asked questions about computed free-will, subjectivity, and other human-like thought patterns.